

Time is Money: The Role of Reallocation Speed Under Capital Constraints

Austin Bennett, Circle Research

`austin.bennett@circle.com`

December 3rd, 2025

Abstract

Capital-constrained businesses often decide between supporting additional blockchains or maintaining higher liquidity for their protocols across existing blockchains. This paper develops a general model to quantify how the speed and cost of cross-chain capital allocation affect capital efficiency gains. We introduce a conservative estimate for per-period gains that can be constructed with two inputs: the cost differential between reallocation options and the incremental revenue unlocked by faster allocation at potentially less capital. Under this model, businesses obtain capital efficiency gains when the value of newly accessible opportunities from faster cross-chain speeds outweighs the additional costs of reallocation.

Keywords— Capital Efficiency; Cross-Chain Allocation; Bridging; DeFi

1 Introduction

Capital flows across blockchains faster and faster each day. Capital-constrained businesses face a difficult choice: whether to support more blockchains or deepen liquidity on existing ones. The relative value of these two goals is constantly shifting, forcing businesses to guess the optimal allocation strategy. This paper shows a simple way to calculate the tradeoff. We present a general mathematical model that examines how the speed and costs of reallocating capital with cross-chain protocols affect capital efficiency gains.

Under this model, speed becomes a decisive variable. Businesses need to weigh the costs of missed opportunities and idle capital against higher fees. Given multiple cross-chain reallocation options, we derive a surprisingly intuitive, conservative estimate for capital efficiency gains under the model.

We form it with two parameters: (1) the cost difference between cross-chain reallocation options and (2) the difference in maximum profitability at post-transfer capital levels. We'll show that within each time period the sum of these two values provides a conservative estimate of a business's capital efficiency gain. In doing so, we demonstrate the fundamental tie between time and money within cross-chain liquidity.

2 Time is Money

Profit opportunities frequently require real-time access to liquidity, but capital can't be everywhere at once. For this reason, businesses use cross-chain reallocation protocols (e.g. bridges, exchanges) to achieve more efficient allocations. Using this strategy, a business's set of profitable opportunities is limited both by the amount of capital on a blockchain and the speed at which they can dispense it. If a cross-chain protocol is both the cheapest and fastest on the market, it's optimal to use it. Oftentimes, however, quicker protocols are more expensive, so businesses must consider both speed and cost to evaluate profits.

The tradeoff of speed and cost is well-studied. An empirical analysis of cross-chain arbitrage across nine blockchains in Öz et al. (2025) revealed that 66.96% of trades relied upon pre-positioned capital inventory, meaning that they did not rely on cross-chain bridging. The authors claim that this could be due to opportunity costs associated with bridge latency, sometimes outweighing the holding costs of capital.

To combat this, intent providers such as Across Protocol (2021) use relayers to dispense capital more quickly. Relayers temporarily front funds on the destination chain for a fee before being reimbursed shortly thereafter. Intents give protocols much quicker access to cross-chain liquidity, which can help businesses keep their assets flexible. Recently, this approach has been heralded as an interoperability solution with the Ethereum Foundation partnering with intent fillers to create the Open Intents Framework (2025).

With the wide-ranging options for cross-chain capital allocations, our task is to value the benefits of increased cross-chain transfer speeds at the expense of cost. A faster, more expensive protocol may leave businesses with less capital, but it can also unlock higher profits from capital allocations. We will show when the additional expense is worth it from a capital efficiency perspective.

3 A Simplified Example

3.1 Sample Profit Opportunity Space

Let's consider a simplified scenario with 4 profit opportunities across 2 blockchains where transfers happen with a fast or slow protocol. Assume the opportunities require some amount of capital. Further, assume each opportunity requires either having the requisite capital onchain or using the fast cross-chain protocol. We list sample profit opportunities in the table below:

Opportunity	Blockchain	Required Capital	Profit Made
1	A	\$25	\$0.08
2	A	\$75	\$0.15
3	B	\$25	\$0.05
4	B	\$75	\$0.20

Assume that using the slow protocol is free and businesses maximize profit. Depending on how much capital the business has and the costs of the fast protocol, the profit opportunities available to a business will change. We consider examples in three different cases.

3.2 Case 1: Fast Protocol has no additional costs

In this case, we get additional speed for free. For this reason, the fast protocol can access any set of profitable opportunities that the slow protocol can as well as any that may be previously barred by low speeds. Since we're selecting from a superset of profit opportunities, the fast protocol will always be at least as capital efficient as the slow protocol, regardless of capital level.

3.3 Case 2: Fast Protocol costs more but increases profits

Assume the fast protocol costs \$0.10. Consider a business that has \$100.10 and splits their capital evenly between the two blockchains. Using the cheaper and slower protocol, the business will only be able to use the capital they've pre-allocated onchain. Thus, they can only access opportunities 1 and 3. Using the fast protocol, however, they can access all opportunities.

Figure 1: Example showing expanded opportunities with a fast protocol.

The best option for the slow protocol is taking opportunities 1 and 3, but for the fast protocol, we can take opportunities 1 and 4. Thus, the fast protocol is more capital efficient, even with higher costs. As we see in this example, Case 2 requires the additional profitability of the fast protocol to be sufficiently large to cover any difference in protocol costs.

3.4 Case 3: Fast Protocol costs more and decreases profits

Assume the faster protocol still costs \$0.10; but now, consider a business that has \$150.00. Using the slow protocol, this is sufficient capital to obtain the most profitable opportunities from pre-positioning capital with an even split. If we use the fast protocol, however, our capital level is now \$149.90, so we cannot take advantage of profit opportunities requiring \$75 on both chains.

Figure 2: Example showing expanded opportunities with a cheaper protocol.

In this example, it will be more capital efficient to use the slow protocol as we have better profit opportunities available. We'll also save on the costs of using the fast protocol. This case can happen even if the fast protocol yields more profit than the slow protocol, when the costs of achieving this additional profitability outweigh any benefit.

4 Capital Efficiency Model

4.1 Overview

The prior examples show a single reallocation decision over two blockchains, but we want to model this relationship over many periods of time and across many blockchains. We can achieve a lower bound for capital efficiency gains by summing per-period profit within each reallocation period.

To simplify, assume businesses use the slower protocol and select optimal reallocation times accordingly. Therefore, the ensuing comparison is based off of the optimal reallocation times for the slower protocol. A faster protocol likely has different optimal times for reallocation; however, we're only solving for a lower bound on the additional profitability from using a faster protocol, so we

use the optimal times for the slower protocol for comparison. Furthermore, assume there are no transfer limits for a cross-chain protocol.

4.2 Model Setup

4.2.1 Variables

First define the following simplified mathematical model of capital allocation:

- $P \in \mathbb{N}$ – Time periods, each separated by a liquidity reallocation.
- $B \in \mathbb{N}$ – Total number of blockchains available to a protocol.
- $I \in \mathbb{R}^P$ – Total available capital per time period.
- $F \in \mathbb{N}$ – Total number of available cross-chain protocols.
- $(R_p^f, \tau_p^f) \in (\mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R})^{P \times F}$ – The expected costs of reallocating capital as well as corresponding reallocation speed by protocol per period.
- $A \in \mathbb{R}^{P \times B}$ – Capital allocations to each blockchain per time period.

4.2.2 Functions

Next, define the following functions for evaluation.

Profit Opportunities Function: $O : \mathbb{R} \times \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^n$

- Function that maps the capital allocation per blockchain and reallocation speed to the set of available profit opportunities for that blockchain.

Value Function: $V : \mathbb{R}^n \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

- Function that maps the selected profit opportunities to profit. This includes all potential fees and revenue that a business faces on each profit opportunity as well as any in-flight capital trapped by low transfer speeds.

Costs of Capital Function: $K : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

- Function that gives costs of holding capital in a given period.

Benefits of Idle Capital Function: $U : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$

- Function that gives benefits of idle capital in a given period.

4.3 Optimizing Profits

4.3.1 Constraints

In any given period, businesses cannot allocate more capital than they have available to them. Thus, the sum of the capital allocated across each blockchain and total reallocation cost cannot exceed the total capital available.

This yields the constraint:

$$\sum_{b=1}^B A_{p,b} \leq I_p - R_p^f, \forall p \in \{1, \dots, P\}$$

4.3.2 Optimization Problem

For simplicity, we first define a business's unused capital as the slack from their available capital in a period: $L_p = I_p - R_p^f - \sum_{b=1}^B A_{p,b}$.

For a cross-chain protocol, a business's profit will be their profit minus their costs of capital, yielding the following optimization problem for each period, p :

$$\max_{A \in \mathbb{R}^{P \times B}} \left(\sum_{b=1}^B V(O(A_{p,b}, \tau_p^f)) \right) + U(L_p) - K(I_p) - R_p^f \quad (1)$$

$$\text{s.t.} \quad \sum_{b=1}^B A_{p,b} \leq I_p - R_p^f \quad (2)$$

4.4 Comparing Optimal Values

4.4.1 Fixing Period and Amount of Capital

Assume we have a faster protocol, F , and a slower protocol, S . We maximize over the reallocation periods for S and define the optimal values for each period:

- Reallocation costs with faster protocol – R_p^{F*}
- Reallocation costs with slower protocol – R_p^{S*}
- Profit opportunities selected with faster protocol – $O^{F*}(A_{p,b}^{F*}, \tau_p^{F*})$
- Profit opportunities selected with slower protocol – $O^{S*}(A_{p,b}^{S*}, \tau_p^{S*})$
- Amount of idle capital with faster protocol – L_p^{F*}
- Amount of idle capital with slower protocol – L_p^{S*}

4.4.2 Per-period Difference in Optimal Profits

Assuming the available capital per period, I_p , is the same, we calculate per reallocation period using these optimal values:

1. Profit Difference: $\sum_{b=1}^B V(O^{F^*}(A_{p,b}^{F^*}, \tau_p^{F^*})) - V(O^{S^*}(A_{p,b}^{S^*}, \tau_p^{S^*}))$
2. Unused Capital Benefits Difference: $U(L_p^{F^*}) - U(L_p^{S^*})$
3. Reallocation Cost Difference: $-R_p^{F^*} + R_p^{S^*}$

This yields the profit gains from capital efficiency for a given period, p :

$$E_p = \left(\sum_{b=1}^B V(O^{F^*}(A_{p,b}^{F^*}, \tau_p^{F^*})) - V(O^{S^*}(A_{p,b}^{S^*}, \tau_p^{S^*})) \right) + U(L_p^{F^*}) - U(L_p^{S^*}) - (R_p^{F^*} - R_p^{S^*})$$

4.5 When Speed is Optimal

4.5.1 Condition by Period

Using the faster protocol, F , will provide capital efficiency gains when $E_p \geq 0$. More intuitively, this will happen when the benefit of the profit opportunities unlocked by speed exceeds the difference in cost for using the faster protocol:

$$\underbrace{\left(\sum_{b=1}^B V(O^{F^*}(A_{p,b}^{F^*}, \tau_p^{F^*})) - V(O^{S^*}(A_{p,b}^{S^*}, \tau_p^{S^*})) \right) + U(L_p^{F^*}) - U(L_p^{S^*})}_{\text{Profit gains from using faster protocol's set of profit opportunities}} \geq \underbrace{R_p^{F^*} - R_p^{S^*}}_{\text{Cost Difference}}$$

To see when this holds, we consider two cases: when the faster protocol is cheaper or the same cost as a slower protocol and when it's more expensive.

4.5.2 Case 1: Faster protocol is cheaper or cost equivalent

Here, we have that $R_p^F \leq R_p^S$. Thus, the options for $O^{S^*}(A_{p,b}^{S^*}, \tau_p^{S^*})$ will be a subset of those for $O^{F^*}(A_{p,b}^{F^*}, \tau_p^{F^*})$ as we have at least as much capital and faster speeds. Since the set of options with the faster protocol is a superset of those with the slower protocol, we have:

$$\sum_{b=1}^B V(O^{F^*}(A_{p,b}^{F^*}, \tau_p^{F^*})) + U(L_p^{F^*}) - U(L_p^{S^*}) \geq \sum_{b=1}^B V(O^{S^*}(A_{p,b}^{S^*}, \tau_p^{S^*}))$$

Since we also know that the faster protocol is cheaper or has equivalent costs to the slower protocol, we combine to obtain the following:

$$\left(\sum_{b=1}^B V(O^{F*}(A_{p,b}^{F*}, \tau_p^{F*})) - V(O^{S*}(A_{p,b}^{S*}, \tau_p^{S*})) \right) + U(L_p^{F*}) - U(L_p^{S*}) \geq 0 \geq R_p^{F*} - R_p^{S*}$$

Thus, $E_p \geq 0$, so the faster protocol always yields capital efficiency gains.

4.5.3 Case 2: The faster protocol is more expensive

Here, neither set necessarily contains the other: some profit opportunities could be too expensive for the faster protocol, some profit opportunities may require more speed than the slower protocol provides. Since the faster protocol will only yield capital efficiency gains when $E_p \geq 0$, the additional profit opportunities gained from speed must be valuable such that two conditions are met:

1. The faster protocol's speed allows for a set of profit opportunities that are more profitable even with less capital.
2. That additional profitability exceeds the increased reallocation costs.

If either of those two conditions are not met, the faster protocol will not provide capital efficiency gains, so the business will opt not to switch and take no difference in profit gains. Otherwise, we take E_p as the profitability gains.

4.5.4 Calculating Total Capital Efficiency Gains

Depending on a variety of factors including estimated profit opportunity availability, gas fees, and protocol fees, faster protocols may yield capital efficiency gains in some periods and not in others. Thus, the minimum capital efficiency gain over our P periods is as follows:

$$\text{Minimum Capital Efficiency Gains: } E = \sum_{p=1}^P \max(E_p, 0)$$

5 Applications of E

5.1 E as a Lower Bound

E serves as a back-of-the-envelope lower bound estimate for capital efficiency gains; however, it is likely an underestimate for two reasons. First, additional profits obtained by the faster protocol could lead to reinvestment effects in future periods. Second, when evaluating the faster protocol, we hold reallocation times fixed to those chosen optimally under the slower protocol. The faster protocol likely has different optimal reallocation times that would increase profitability.

5.2 Using E to Determine Flexible Capital

Faster cross-chain protocols can have diminishing returns with respect to the capital they transfer. For example, a blockchain solver may use a slower, cheaper protocol for consistent volume without speed requirements for some portion of capital, but a faster protocol to keep a flexible balance for liquidity events.

The model still applies. Set the total allocation amount equal to this flexible amount you wish to use and repeat the analysis. For many businesses, the fast protocol may yield additional profit up to a specific amount. We show a simplified example of this below, where the top line is profit for the fast protocol and bottom line is profit for the slow protocol, until they cross and reverse.

Figure 3: Simplified profit for a business that benefits a lot from speed.

The additional profit for a faster protocol will depend on numerous factors including risk, strategy, costs, and capital. For businesses that target predictable profit opportunities and don't benefit significantly from faster cross-chain transfer speed, this will likely be far smaller as shown in the example below.

Figure 4: Simplified profit for a business that benefits little from speed.

In any case, a business will allocate capital to the point where the additional profit from using the fast protocol yields the same benefit as the additional costs of using the fast protocol. This is the optimal usage of the fast protocol. Any amount before this leaves profit opportunities lost to speed, but any amount after this incurs unnecessary costs, potentially reducing the profit opportunities.

It's entirely possible that the fast protocol does not offer any additional capital efficiency gains; and in that case, a business allocates nothing to the fast protocol. That being said, in many cases some allocation to a faster protocol will yield additional profit. The question for businesses then becomes one of predicting what the optimal allocation is.

5.3 Limitations and Future Work

5.3.1 Determining Feasible Sets for Profit Opportunities

Determining the unlocked opportunities from higher speeds is difficult. A business could optimize over their sets of profit opportunities under different protocols, but this is often computationally infeasible and may not accurately estimate opportunities in subsequent periods. For this paper, we intentionally specify the model with broad value and option functions. This is so the model can apply beyond blockchain solvers and cross-chain wallet providers. Future work should be done to better approximate the value and option functions within specific use cases.

5.3.2 Total Profitability

While E provides a lower bound for profit gains from capital efficiency, it may not accurately represent total profitability. Businesses should also consider their implementation and risk costs associated with using different protocols. This paper only discusses capital efficiency. In many cases, we may see capital efficiency gains, but the costs of using such a cross-chain protocol may outweigh the capital efficiency gains.

Examining the benefits of using protocols with multiple speeds helps businesses better understand this balance. In doing so, they could put their capital to work efficiently. Not only might this help their profit margins, but it could also expand access to their services. Hopefully, this brings us closer to an interoperable future where capital flows freely and efficiently.

References

- Across Protocol (2021). *Instant Trustless Token Transfers from Rollup to Mainnet*. accessed: 2025-10-09. URL: <https://drive.google.com/file/d/1t9tJUjJupLSvHKR8glwLKh8kpBNp5sp1/view>.
- Open Intents Framework (2025). *Open Intents Framework: Intents as a Public Good*. accessed: 2025-10-09. URL: <https://www.openintents.xyz/#1976d35200d6811c8ac4d53baf4fbcf5>.
- Öz, Burak, Christof Ferreira Torres, Christoph Schlegel, Bruno Mazorra, Jonas Gebele, Filip Rezabek, and Florian Matthes (2025). *Cross-Chain Arbitrage: The Next Frontier of MEV in Decentralized Finance*. arXiv: 2501.17335 [cs.CR]. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2501.17335>.